

Project BioCombs4Nanofibers

D2.7 Physico-chemical properties of capture wool and its interaction with the calamistrum of cribellate spiders

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1. Goals and Detailed Description

Overall goal: **D2.7 Physico-chemical properties of capture wool and its interaction with the calamistrum of cribellate spiders** is a public report on the web-site on new findings about cribellate spiders and is directly connected to Objective 1. It will refer to a scientific article on these results.

Objective 1 Calamistrum: Experimental and theoretical evidence that the nanostructures on the calamistrum have the function to avoid self-adhesion to the cribellate nanofibers **for at least four different species of spiders** (m27).

Cribellate spiders produce a nanofibrous wool to capture prey. Therefore, they use a comb on their hind (fourth) leg, the calamistrum, brushing over the nanofibers repeatedly. We removed the calamistra of four cribellate species, studying the impact of this removal on the capture thread production: *Uloborus plumipes* (Joel *et al.* 2020), *Amaurobius similis*, *Eresus walckenaeri*, and *Kukulcania hibernalis*. For shaving, the spiders were first anaesthetized with diethyl ether and immobilized by fixing them to a preparation dish with minutiae. Under the microscope, the calamistral setae were removed by carefully sweeping along the metatarsus of the fourth legs using small pieces broken glass (cover slip) (Image 1). The spiders were then released back into their retreat. After several days to weeks, either the exuviae were collected or the animals were killed (freezing to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). In case of complete animals, the specimens were air-dried, and both, exuviae or air-dried animal, sputter coated with gold for SEM imaging.

Image 1: Setup (left) to remove the calamistra of spiders. In the middle, a full shot of pinned-down *U. plumipes* is presented and the close-up on the right site is the leg of *K. hibernalis*, still with calamistrum.

The shaved areas of the metatarsus in all four species were clearly visible by the remaining epithelial sheaths (Image 2, 3). At higher magnification (Image 2 c, f, Image 3), residues of various silk fibers were visible on the cuticle of the spiders. This adhesion of fibers on the metatarsus, leading to a clotting of the complete area, was not observed in non-shaved spiders. Hence, the calamistra of all four species have antiadhesive properties towards nanofibers.

Image 2: Effect of the shaving of calamistra in cribellate spiders. (a, d) Before shaving, the calamistrum of *Amaurobius similis* (a) consists of two rows of calamistrual setae (highlighted by dashed red box). The calamistrum of *Eresus walckenaeri* consists of one row of setae (red arrow) and a broad field of further calamistrual setae. (b, e) After shaving, the setae were removed so that only the epithelial sheaths of the setae were left (dashed red box). (c, f) In a close-up, one could see that the entire surface of the shaved areas on the metatarsus was covered by different types of silken fibers.

Image 3: Close-up of the clotted metatarsus of *Uloborus plumipes* (Joel *et al.* 2020).

As we measure forces between cribellate threads and calamistrum (respectively biomimetic structured surface) indirectly via thread deflection (see our public deliverable **D2.4 Adhesion measurements of natural and artificial fibers** at the project website <http://biocombs4nanofibers.eu>), we have to analyze whether the mechanical properties of the cribellate thread is influenced by surface chemistry or ambient climate. We observed that the interaction with prey cuticular hydrocarbons (CHC) not only increases adhesion (Bott *et al.* 2017) between prey and thread, but also strongly influence e.g. the elasticity of the cribellate thread (Image 4). We coated metal clips with the CHCs of the cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* and measured the maximum elongation of the thread before break in native (i.e. untreated) and CHC-treated cribellate capture threads of *Uloborus plumipes*. The stretchability strongly decreases after contact with CHCs (Baumgart *et al.* Change of mechanical characteristics in cribellate capture threads after contact with prey. In preparation).

Image 4: Migration of cuticular hydrocarbons into the cribellate capture thread reduced the elasticity of the threads.

However, we never observed any CHC migration into the threads after contact with spider legs. Currently we investigate whether the viscosity of the spider's CHC is too high for such interaction. In any case, our experiments and theoretical modelling suggest, that rather than surface chemistry, the antiadhesive properties are influenced by the surface structure (Joel *et al.* 2020). We characterized the properties of the threads under changing climatic conditions (Meyer *et al.* 2021). Therefore, capture threads of *Uloborus plumipes* were brought into contact with unstructured and biomimetically structured foils, mimicking the calamistrum topography. Already for the unstructured foils, we could see a change in the stretchability of the fibers (either by changed mechanical properties or by changed adhesion to the foil. These two effects are not discriminable with our setup): whereas temperature had no significant impact on the deflection of the nanofibers, increasing humidity also lead to an increased deflection of the thread, with significant differences at least for both extremes (10 % vs 90 %, $p = 0.02$) (Image 5).

Image 5: The deflection of threads in contact with unstructured surfaces was influenced by high humidity but not by temperature. Shown are the averaged maximum deflections of the threads before detaching from the surfaces. **(left)** Comparison of unstructured foil at different relative humidity levels but constant temperature ($T = 20\text{ °C}$); **(right)** Comparison of unstructured foil at different temperatures but constant humidity ($RH = 50\%$). $n = 25$ each. Significant differences between groups were determined by ANOVA with subsequent Tukey post-hoc test. *: $p < 0.05$.

In the structured samples, a humidity increase lead to an increased adhesion even before the control samples would indicate so. However, the antiadhesive effect in general was not hampered due to humidity. In contrast, though the mechanical properties seem not to be influenced by temperature, the anti-adhesive effect vanished at temperatures above 30 °C (Image 6).

Image 6. The anti-adhesive effect was not hampered due to humidity but temperature influenced the effect greatly. Shown are the averaged maximum deflections of the threads before detaching from the surface. In the area above, the difference of the deflections between control and structured PET (in %) is indicated as well as the statistical relevance. **(left)** Comparison of LIPSS and control foil at different relative humidity levels but constant temperature ($T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$); **(right)** Comparison of LIPSS and control foil at different temperatures but constant humidity (RH = 50%). $n = 25$ each. Significant differences between LIPSS and control foils were determined by a Wilcoxon t -test. *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant. (Meyer *et al.* 2021)

We additionally characterized the chemistry of cribellate threads (i.e. axial fibers, paracribellate fibers and cribellate nanofibers, as all three were not dissociable). Together with Sean Blamires and a team of the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre at the University of New South Wales (Sydney, Australia), we performed a GC-MS analysis of the silk and compared it to major ampullate (i.e. dragline) silk of *Nephila plumipes* and *Uloborus plumipes* (Image 7, Joel *et al.* Physico-chemical properties of spider silk nanofibers. In preparation). In the cribellate silk of *Uloborus plumipes*, less glycine could be detected, but therefore a higher amount of serine and nonpolar amino acids in general. This is strange, as glycine is involved in the formation of the typical secondary structure, making spider silk such an extremely tough material.

Image 7: Amino acid composition of the cribellate thread of *Uloborus plumipes* (below) in comparison to its own major ampullate silk (middle) and the silk of *Nephila plumipes*, a spider typically used for silk analysis.

Literature:

Bott, R.A., Baumgartner, W., Bräunig, P., Menzel, F. & Joel, A.-C. (2017) Adhesion enhancement of cribellate capture threads by epicuticular waxes of the insect prey sheds new light on spider web evolution. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 284, 20170363.

Joel, A.-C., Meyer, M., Heitz, J., Heiss, A., Park, D., Adamova, H. & Baumgartner, W. (2020) Biomimetic Combs as Antiadhesive Tools to Manipulate Nanofibers. *ACS Applied Nano Materials*, 3, 3395-3401.

Meyer, M., Buchberger, G., Heitz, J., Baiko, D. & Joel, A.-C. (2021) Ambient Climate Influences Anti-Adhesion between Biomimetic Structured Foil and Nanofibers. *Nanomaterials*, 11, 3222.

2. Evaluation of Goals and Resulting Actions

This report has been finalized and submitted in time in m27. It will be published on the website of the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** project (<http://biocombs4nanofibers.eu>). A reference to this report will also be published on Twitter and ResearchGate as project update for our followers.

Some results presented in this report are already published (Meyer et al., *Nanomaterials*, 2021; Joel et al., *ACS Applied Nano Materials*, 2020). Further results are planned to be published in scientific articles in the journals *Acta Biomaterialia* and *Small*.

With the results of this report, which will be further detailed in the planned publications, the **Objective 1 Calamistrum** is reached by 100%.

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